

DESCRIBING DATA USING NUMERICAL MEASURES

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Annotation: When working with statistical data, researchers need to get acquainted with the data types used—categorical and numerical data. The different data types are used in separate cases and require different statistical and visualization techniques. Therefore, researchers need to understand the different data types and their analysis. This knowledge is what is used during the research process.

Numerical data as a case study is categorized into discrete and continuous data where continuous data are further grouped into interval and ratio data. These data types are significantly used for statistical analysis or research purposes. Numerical data is a data type expressed in numbers, rather than natural language description. Sometimes called quantitative data, numerical data is always collected in number form. Numerical data differentiates itself from other number form data types with its ability to carry out arithmetic operations with these numbers. For example, numerical data of the number of male students and female students in a class may be taken, then added together to get the total number of students in the class. This characteristic is one of the major ways of identifying numerical data.

Numerical data can take 2 different forms, namely; discrete data, which represents countable items and continuous data, which represents data measurement. The continuous type of numerical data is further sub-divided into interval and ratio data, which is known to be used for measuring items. Numerical data examples which are usually expressed in numbers include; census data,

temperature, age, mark grading, annual income, time, height, IQ, CGPA, etc. These numerical examples, either in countable numbers as in discrete data or measurement form like continuous data call all be labeled as an example of numerical data. We will now conduct a statistical analysis based on the following issue.

Issue: The farmer is studying the effects of natural fertilizer applied to the soil on tomato yields. It receives data by applying 5 different amounts of 0, 10, 20, 30, 40 kg of organic fertilizer per 100 kv.m

amount of fertilizer (X)	amount of yield (Y)
0	6
0	8
10	11
10	14
20	18
20	23
30	25
30	28
40	30
40	34

1. Main statistical indicators: Definations, values and conclusion on them.

- a) The mean is the arithmetic average of date values. The most common measure of central tendency. Mean-sum of values divided by the number of values (outliers) $\bar{x} = \frac{x_1+x_2+\dots+x_n}{n}$

b) Moda- a measure of central tendency. Value that occurs most often. Not affected by extreme values. Used for either numerical or categorical data.

There may be no mode or there may be several modes

c) In an ordered array, the median is the “middle” number.

$$x_{med} = x_{\left[\frac{n}{2}\right]+1} \quad \text{- if n or N is odd, the median is the middle number}$$

$$x_{med} = \frac{1}{2} \left(x_{\left[\frac{n}{2}\right]} + x_{\left[\frac{n}{2}\right]+1} \right) \quad \text{- if n or N is even, the median is the average of the two middle number}$$

d) Difference between the largest and the smallest observations. $R = x_{(n)} - x_{(1)}$

e) Average of squared deviations of values from the mean : $S^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2$

f) Inter quartile range: $IQR=Q_3-Q_1$

Variable	Mean	SE Mean	StDev	Minimum	Q1	Median	Q3
x	20,00	4,71	14,91	0,00	7,50	20,00	32,50
y	19,70	3,08	9,74	6,00	10,25	20,50	28,50

1. Grafiklar: gistogramma, Box-Whisker of graph, conclusions.

The Box and central line are centered between the endpoints if data is symmetric around the median.

A Box and Whisker plot can be shown in either vertical or horizontal format.

2. Interval estimation for mean, median, standard deviation based on each composite.

3. Point diagram. Preliminary conclusions

There is strong linear association between the amount of fertilizer applied and the tomato yield obtained and as we increase the amount of fertilizer, the yield increases.

Correlation Coefficient.

The correlation coefficient is computed by dividing the covariance by the product of the standard deviations of the two variables.

Let us be given X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n and Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_n composite.

$$\rho(X, Y) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{nS_x S_y}$$

$-1 \leq r \leq 1$ always holds while S_{xy} depends on the unit of the variables.

If $0 < r \leq 1$, then there is a positive linear association between x and y .

If $-1 \leq r < 0$, then there is a negative linear association between x and y .

If and $r = 0$, then there is no linear association between the variables x and y .

There is exists a strong linear relationship if $|r| \geq \frac{2}{\sqrt{n}}$.

$$\rho(X, Y) = 0,979$$

Then, there is positive linear association between productivity and fertilizer application.

4. The test for Correlation Coefficient

Test to see if the correlation coefficient between the test variables differs significantly from zero.

$$H_0: \rho(X, Y) = 0$$

$$H_a: \rho(X, Y) \neq 0$$

1) $r=0,979$ Correlation Coefficient

2) $s_r = \sqrt{\frac{1-r^2}{n-2}} = 0,089$ standard deviation of the correlation coefficient

$$3) T = \frac{r}{s_r} = 10,87$$

$$4) T_{cr} = 2,3 \quad (-2,3; 2,3)$$

5) $T_{cr} < T$ H_a is appropriate. Then there is no linear association between fertilization and yield.

5. Foundation of the regression equation.

$y = b_0 + b_1x$ is regression equation. Where $b_1 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}$ and $b_0 = \bar{y} - b_1\bar{x}$ are found by the formulas.

The regression equation is

$$y = 6,900 + 0,6400 x$$

$$S = 2,08866 \quad R\text{-Sq} = 95,9\% \quad R\text{-Sq(adj)} = 95,4\%$$

6. Coefficient of determination.

The coefficient of determination is calculated by the following formula.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{SSE}{SST} = \frac{SSR}{SST}$$

There $SST = \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2$, $SSE = \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y})^2$, $SSR = SST - SSE$

$$R\text{-Sq} = 95,9\%$$

7. In conclusion, the increase in productivity can be explained by an increase in the amount of fertilizer applied to the land area of 95.9%.

8. Standard error of assessment.

$$9. S_{xy} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y})^2}{n-2}}$$

10. Represents average scattering. $S = 2.08866$

11. **Test for regression coefficient.**

$$H_0: \beta_1 = 0$$

$$H_a: \beta_1 \neq 0$$

$$1) b_1 = 0,64$$

$$2) S_{b_1} = \frac{S_{xy}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}} = 0,046$$

$$3) T_{b_1} = \frac{b_1}{S_{b_1}} = 13,70 \quad p=0,00001$$

$$4) H_a \text{ gepoteza o'rinli } (\alpha = 0,005)$$

Predictor	Coef	SE Coef	T	P
Constant	6,900	1,144	6,03	0,000
x	0,64000	0,04670	13,70	0,000

12. **Masala uchun F test.**

$$H_0: \rho^2 = 0$$

$$H_a: \rho^2 > 0$$

$$1) R^2 = 0,959$$

2) 2) SSE, SSR, SST are found.

$$3) F = \frac{SSR(n-k)}{SSE(k-1)} = \frac{MSR}{MSE}$$

Source	DF	SS	MS	F	P
Regression	1	819,20	819,20	187,78	0,000
Residual Error	8	34,90	4,36		
Total	9	854,10			

13. Then the hypothesis yes is valid ($\alpha = 0.005$). In short, the change in yield can be expressed in terms of the change in fertilizer applied to the soil.

14. **Predictions for given values. 2 types of confidence intervals.**

The red line is the interval value of the average y for the value x;
 The interval value of one y for the value x given by the green line.

15. Final conclusion on the issue.

Calculations show that the yield of tomatoes is linearly related to the amount of fertilizer applied to it, and when the soil is not fertilized, 100 kv.m about 6.9 kg of land can be harvested, and if we increase the amount of fertilizer applied to these lands by 1kg, the yield will increase by 0.64 kg.

Conclusion

Numerical data research techniques employ inquiry strategies such as experiments and surveys. The findings may be predictive, explanatory, and confirming. It involves the collection of data which is then subjected to statistical treatment to support or refute a hypothesis. Thus, numerical data collection techniques are used to gather data from different reliable sources, which deal with numbers, statistics, charts, graphs, tables. Numerical data is one of the most useful data types in statistical analysis. Formplus provides its users with a repository of great features to go with it. With Formplus's web-based data collection tool, you

have access to features that will assist you in making strategic business decisions. This way, you can improve business sales, launch better products and serve customers better.

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